

CREEP BEHAVIOUR OF LAMINATED GRP IN THREE POINT BENDING

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ABSTRACT

The creep and relaxation behaviours of laminated GRP in three point bending were studied both experimentally and analytically. The creep and relaxation experiments of 8 types of GRP were carried out. The bending deflexion and strains of creep and the load and strain of relaxation were measured, and the creep deflexion and the relaxation strain were predicted.

INTRODUCTION

Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) has long been used and is being increasingly applied to engineering structures and constructions. It has the advantageous properties of high specific strength and modulus. But it shows remarkable visco-elastic effect when it is loaded by bending, shearing and torsional forces and under off-axial tension in respect to the fibre direction. In order to ensure that the structural components of GRP are reliable in service, the designer should know its creep behaviour well and take it into account in design. The relaxation behaviour of CSM-GRP was experimentally studied in the previous paper ¹, the research described in the present paper is concerned with creep and relaxation behaviour of glass fabric reinforced GRP in three point bending. Eight types of GRP beam specimens were tested. The typical creep and relaxation behaviours of one kind of specimen were analysed. The predicted results were compared with experiments, and seen to have reasonable agreement.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

1. Materials and Specimens

The tested materials are 8 types of laminated sheet made of glass fibre fabric reinforced epoxy resin. The specimens are categorised into 8 groups according to their warp to weft ratio and lay-up angle. The configuration and glass fibre content of the specimens are shown in the following table. All the specimens are manufactured according to the NATIONAL STANDARD GB 2567-2578-81.

Table 1 Categories of the specimens

Group Number	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
Warp/weft Ratio	1:1	1:1	4:1	4:1	4:1	7:1	7:1	7:1
Lay-up Angle	0°	+45°	0°	90°	+45°	0°	90°	+45°
Number of Layers	11	11	11	11	11	7	7	7
Volume Fraction of Fibre (%)	29.3	29.4	33.1	31.1	26.9	29.9	31.0	26.0

2. Experiments

The experimental set-up and the dimensions of the specimen are schematically shown in

Fig.1. The tests were conducted by using INSTRON 1195 testing machine. The temperature in the testing chamber is 50°C. When the load, p is kept constant, the variations of deflexion and strains with time were measured, the test is called creep test. If the deflexion of the beam specimen is held to be constant, the load and strain were measured as the functions of time, the test is named as relaxation test. Before these tests, some preliminary tests were performed to measure the Young's modulus E and shear modulus G under the temperature of 50°C.

Fig.1 Experimental scheme and configuration of specimen

3. Experimental Results and Discussion

The creep strain, $\epsilon(t)$ and displacement, $f_{max}(t)$ curves of the 8 kinds of specimens are illustrated in Fig.2 and 3 respectively. It is obvious that the specimens with $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up angle exhibit the most remarkable creep effect, because in addition to transverse shear deformation, the in-plane shear deformation gives a large contribution to the creep strain and displacement. Comparing 0° specimens with the 90° specimens reveals that the former specimens have less creep effect than the latter ones. Among the 0° specimens with the three different warp/weft ratios, the 7:1 specimen has the least creep effect. Figure 4, 5 and 6 are the relaxation strain and load curves. It can be seen that all the load curves decrease monotonically with time. But as for the strain curves, while most curves increase monotonically with time in the duration of test, the curves of the specimens of V-5 and VI-5 increase with time at early stage and after reaching their maximum values turn to decrease, that reveals the complexity of the problem.

THEORETICAL PREDICTION

1. Basic Assumptions

In the three point bending beam undergoing creep and relaxation tests, the strains and stress are all functions of time and coordinate, so the analyses are very complicated. To simplify the calculations the following assumptions were adopted:

Fig.2 Creep strain curves

Fig.3 Creep deflexion curves

- A. The small strain and small deflection assumptions.
- B. The plane cross-section assumption. That is, we assumed that the cross-section of the beam remained flat after deformation, but it was no longer perpendicular to the axis of the beam.
- C. The material subjected to tension has the same behaviour with that subjected to compression. So they can be analysed by using the same constitutive equation.

Fig.4 Relaxation strain curves

Fig.5 Relaxation load curves of 7 specimens

2. Creep Equations

The deflexion in both of creep and relaxation tests can be divided into two parts: pure bending deflexion and the transverse shear deflexion. The following equation was used to calculate the pure bending deflexion of creep test².

$$\epsilon_c = \frac{\sigma}{E} + A\sigma^m (1 - e^{-qt}) + B\sigma^n t \quad (1)$$

The first term on the right side of Eq.1 refers to the elastic strain. The second and third terms are for the transient and steady creep stages respectively. For relaxation, the pure bending deflexion was analysed by using the generalised creep equation³:

$$\ddot{\epsilon} + q\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\ddot{\sigma}}{E} + (q\dot{\phi} + \dot{\psi} + \frac{q\dot{\sigma}}{E}) + q\psi \quad (2)$$

where $\phi = A\sigma^m$, $\psi = B\sigma^n$.

As for the creep equation of transverse shear creep effect, it was assumed that the transverse shear deflexion could be approximately estimated by one-term equation which corresponds to the steady stage of creep. The equivalent stress and equivalent strain for a pure shear stress state are given as

$$\sigma^* = \sqrt{3}\tau, \quad \epsilon^* = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\gamma \quad (3)$$

The relationship between σ^* and ϵ^* is

$$\dot{\epsilon}^* = B\sigma^{*n} \quad (4)$$

Then

$$\dot{\gamma} = 3 \frac{n+1}{2} B\tau^n \quad (5)$$

3. Experimental Determination of the Constants in Eq.1

The following analysis will proceed in the following procedure. The 5 constants of Eq.1, A, B, m, n and q will be determined experimentally first, then by using creep Eq.1 the deflexion of the beam will be calculated. The two constants, B and n were determined by referring Fig.7 and using the following formula:

$$n = \ln (s_1/s_2) / \ln (x_1/x_2) \quad (6)$$

where s_1 and s_2 are the slopes of the creep curves at the steady stage, x_1 and x_2 are the coordinates of the two strain gages on the bending specimen.

$$B = s_1 \sigma_{1T}^{-n} \quad (7)$$

The letter T of the subscript refers to steady creep stage.

From the measurements of the transient creep stage, the constants A and m were calculated by using the following formulas:

$$m = \frac{\ln (\epsilon_{r1} / \epsilon_{r2})}{\ln (x_1 / x_2)} \quad (8)$$

ϵ_{ri} are as shown in Fig.7.

$$A = \epsilon_{r1} \sigma_{1T}^{-m} \quad (9)$$

The constant q was determined by a quasi-least-square method. A initial value q_0 was approximated by substituting a estimated value of stress σ_0 into Eq 1. The modification of q can be calculated through the formula

$$\Delta q = \frac{\sum_1^N (\epsilon - \epsilon_i) e^{-q_0 t_i} t_i}{\sum_1^N (e^{-2q_0 t_i} t_i^2) A \sigma_0^n} \quad (10)$$

$$q = q_0 + \Delta q \quad (11)$$

Fig.6 Relaxation load curve of specimen VI-5

Fig.7 Creep strain curves used for determining the constants in Eq.1

4. Solution of the Creep Deflexion

A. The deflexion of pure bending: Based on the solution of Ref. 2, the pure bending creep deflexion f_d can be obtained by intergration of the following equation.

$$h \frac{d^2 f_d}{d x^2} = K_1 M + K_2 M^m + K_3 M^n \quad (12)$$

where M is bending moment and equals to ax , K_1 , K_2 and K_3 can be found from Ref. 2. Upon integration and use of boundary conditions, we obtained

$$f_d = \frac{K_1 Q}{6h} x^3 + \frac{K_2 Q^m}{(m+1)(m+2)h} x^{m+2} + \frac{K_3 Q^n}{h(n+1)(n+2)} x^{n+2} - \frac{x}{h} \left[K_1 Q \frac{a^2}{2} + K_2 Q^m \frac{a^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{K_3 Q^n}{n+1} a^{n+1} \right] \quad (13)$$

B. The transverse shear deflexion: The creep stress at the steady stage can be expressed as ²

$$\sigma_T = \frac{2n+1}{n} \left(\frac{y}{h}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \frac{M}{2bh^3} \quad (14)$$

Making use of the equilibrium equation and the boundary conditions, we obtained the expression of shear stress

$$\tau_T = \frac{1+2n}{1+n} \frac{Q}{2bh} \left[1 - \left(\frac{y}{h}\right)^{1+\frac{1}{n}} \right] \quad (15)$$

Substituting the above equation into Eq.5 and letting $y=0$, the shear strain at the middle surface of the beam was derived as

$$\gamma \Big|_{y=0} = \frac{3}{4} \frac{Q}{bhG} + \frac{3^{(n+1)/2}}{2} B \left(\frac{1+2n}{1+n} \frac{Q}{2bh} \right)^n t \quad (16)$$

According to the Timoshenko Beam Theory, the slope of the deflexion caused by the transverse shear force is equal to shear strain of the beam at the central surface, ie

$$\frac{df_s}{dx} = \gamma \Big|_{y=0} \quad (17)$$

Thus, the transverse shear deflexion of the beam was obtained through a simple integration

$$f_s = \frac{3}{2} \frac{QX}{2bhG} + \frac{3^{(n+1)/2}}{2} B \left(\frac{1+2n}{1+n} \frac{Q}{2bh} \right)^n xt \quad (18)$$

The deflexion of the central point of the beam span is

$$f_{max} = [f_s + f_d]_{x=a} \quad (19)$$

5. Numerical Results

The creep deflexion of the specimen II-1 was calculated. Its warp/weft ratio is 1:1, and lay-up angle is $\pm 45^\circ$. The dimensions of the specimen are: $b=14.9\text{mm}$, $h=1.6\text{mm}$, $2a=70\text{mm}$. The coordinates of the two strain gages are: $x_D=14.5\text{mm}$, $x_C=33\text{mm}$. The creep load, p is kept constant, $p=2Q=8\text{Kg}$.

In the preliminary tests, the material initial elastic moduli were measured under 50°C , $E=850\text{ kg/mm}^2$, $G=18\text{ kg/mm}^2$. The 5 constants of Eq.1 were determined through the procedure described above. $A=21.7926 \times 10^{-6}$, $B=6.4796 \times 10^{-6}$. $m=2.03558$, $n=1.8061$, $q=0.3466/\text{min}$.

The creep deflexion curve predicted is shown in Fig.8 by the broken line. It is in reasonable agreement with the measured curve of the solid line.

But, the deviation between the experimental and the calculated results is obvious. It was probably caused by the approximation of the basic assumptions, based upon which the predicted results was derived.

Fig.8 Comparison of predicted and measured creep strain curves

The relaxation strain curve was also predicted by using Eq.2 and compared with the measured one. Because of the limitation of the length of the paper, it cannot be presented here and will be published else-where.

CONCLUSION

The creep and relaxation behaviours of 8 types of GRP were studied. Remarkable creep effect was seen and therefore should be taken into consideration in the design of structures made of these kinds of materials. Based upon the existing formulas for creep deflexion of pure bending beam, the creep deflexion of the laminated GRP was calculated. In so doing, the transverse shear effect was taken into account. The predicted result of creep deflexion proved to be reasonable.

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